

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

EFFECT OF SODIUM ALGINATE ENTRAPPED AM FUNGAL INOCULUM ON GROWTH AND NUTRITION OF GARLIC (*ALLIUM SATIVUM* L.) VARIETIES IN NILGIRI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 14/05/2017

Available online
17/06/2017

Keywords

AMF,
Garlic,
G. Aggregatum,
Nilgiri District,
Nutrition,
Sodium Alginate.

ABSTRACT

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) is one of the most important bulb vegetable, which is used as spice and flavoring agent for foods. It is an important crop grown in the hills of Tamilnadu. Garlic is rich in nutrients and used medicinally to cure number of diseases. In order to improve the productivity and high nutrient content of Garlic, biofertilizers are recommended. Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi gained significant importance in horticulture, agriculture etc. Hence in the present study, the effect of sodium alginate entrapped AMF inoculum in growth and nutrition of Garlic varieties in Nilgiri District was investigated. Inoculation with AMF, *G. aggregatum* as alginate entrapped inoculum produced plants with greater height, number of leaves, plant biomass, sizes of bulb and increased nutrition viz., nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium content of Garlic varieties when compared to the control. Different carrier based sodium alginate entrapped *G. aggregatum* against varieties of Garlic were also analysed. It is concluded that the native strain of *G. aggregatum* along with the sodium alginate entrapped inoculum is suitable for the cultivation of native garlic varieties in Nilgiris District.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr. S. Rajesh Kumar** et al. Effect of Sodium Alginate Entrapped AM Fungal Inoculum on Growth And Nutrition of Garlic (*Allium Sativum* L.) Varieties in Nilgiri District, Tamilnadu, India. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(05).

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INTRODUCTION

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) is one of the most important bulb vegetable, which is used as spice and flavoring agent for foods [1]. Garlic is rich in sugar, protein, fat, calcium, potassium, phosphorus, sulphur, iodine, fibre and silicon, in addition to vitamins [2]. Medicinally garlic is used against arteriosclerosis, high blood pressure, and has been shown to have antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral and antiprotozoal activities [3].

In India, 52 spices are identified as commercially important. Among the different crops cultivated in India, Garlic is considered as one of the important food, spices and medicinal crop. India ranks second to China in area and production of Garlic, but ranks 74th for Garlic in terms of productivity (FAOSTAT, 2010). Madhya Pradesh is the major garlic producing state, followed by Gujarat and UP. Garlic, is an important crop grown in the hills of Tamilnadu. In Tamilnadu, garlic produced 3.1 lakh metric tons from 0.4 lakh hectares [4] and Nilgiri district contribute a considerable amount in terms of productivity.

The usage of chemical fertilizers and over exploitation of natural resources, the productivity of crops has reduced. Biofertilizers become more important component to compensate the integrated nutrient supply system and hold a promise for sustaining the productivity of crops over a long period. Among biofertilizers mycorrhizae play an important role. Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) are the most common types of all mycorrhizae. In recent years, AM fungi gained significant importance in horticulture, agriculture and even in afforestation and land reclamation [5]. AMF or endomycorrhizae are one such group of beneficial organisms known to benefit the host plants in a variety of ways [6]. AMF are obligate symbiont associated with roots of more than 80% of the terrestrial plants including most agricultural plants [7]. AMF promotes growth and also in uptake of nutrients especially phosphorus [8]. Therefore, using native AMF as a bioinoculant for improving growth and productivity are increasingly realized especially in bulbous crop like Garlic.

The widely used method for obtaining AMF inoculum has been the use of root segments of plants hosting AMF [9]. However, these inocula are voluminous, heavy and often contaminated by other organisms [10]. Successful entrapment of AMF propagules have been achieved in seeds resulting in successful germination and colonization of AMF [11]. Often, alginates are used as inoculant carriers for AMF [12,13]. Hence in the present study, the effect of sodium alginate entrapped AMF inoculum in growth and nutrition of Garlic varieties in Nilgiri District, Tamilnadu, India was investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Production of alginate entrapped AM inoculum

In this experiment, *Glomus aggregatum* was used for the production of alginate entrapped AM inoculum. Sand: soil mixture containing chlamydo spores and infected root segments (chopped) of *Allium cepa* infected with *Glomus aggregatum* grown for 90 days served [14,15] as the mycorrhizal inoculum. The inoculum was air dried and passed through 425 μm sieve. To an aqueous suspension of sodium alginate 2 per cent (2 gm in 100 ml of distilled water boil at 80°C), 10 per cent (10 gm) of the sieved sand: soil inoculum of the AM fungus and 2 per cent (2 gm) of the carrier material (perlite, soilrite vermiculite and talc) were added separately and mixed using a magnetic stirrer.

This mixture was taken in a syringe and added drop wise in 0.1 M sterile calcium chloride solution to form beads. After 30 minutes the beaded inoculum was rinsed with tap water. A portion of the alginate entrapped wet AM inoculum was dried to surface dryness and stored at 4°C. This formed the carrier based alginate entrapped AM inoculum. A portion of the beads were air dried for 5 days to form dry AM alginate inoculum packed in polythene bags, and stored at room temperature (32 \pm -5°C).

The pH of the carrier materials used in this study was estimated by using a digital pH meter (substrate; water ratio = 1:10 w/v). After drying to a constant weight, the moisture content of the wet AM beads were determined. The number of propagules in the different carrier based alginate entrapped AM inoculum was determined by the most probable number (MPN) method using fourfold dilutions [16]. The alginate beads were solubilized in 0.2 M sodium citrate solution (pH adjusted to 7.2) prior to carrying out the MPN test. The propagule numbers in the dry AM alginate beads was compared from the propagule numbers of the wet AM alginate beads and its moisture content.

Effect of alginate entrapped AM inoculums on garlic varieties

A pot culture experiment was also conducted to know the effect of alginate entrapped AM (*G. aggregatum*) inoculum on the colonization of roots and growth of *Allium sativum* as the host plant. The soil used for this study was sandy loam soil of pH 7.2, with 2.4 mg available P/g (NH₄ + HCl extractable) and an indigenous AM population of 0.31 propagules/g of soil. Plastic pots (12 cm dia) were filled with 1L of soil and inoculated with alginate entrapped wet and dry AM inoculum (with perlite, soilrite, vermiculite and talc as carriers) and sand: soil inoculum of *Glomus aggregatum* separately taken at the rate of 300 propagules per pot. One clove each per pot was arranged in a green-house (temperature 29 \pm 2°C) in randomized complete block design and watered whenever necessary. 50 ml of Ruakura nutrient solution was added thrice (First application with P, 20 days after planting and the other two later applications without P, on 40 and 60 days after planting).

Observations on plant height were recorded on hundred and twenty days after planting. The plants were harvested 120 days after planting. Plant samples were dried in the oven at 60°C to a constant weight to get plant biomass. The bulb polar, equatorial diameter and neck thickness were measured. Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium content of the shoot and bulb samples were determined, by the vanadomolybdate phosphoric yellow colour method [17] and flame photometric method respectively. Mycorrhizal colonization of the root was determined by the gridline-intersect method [15] after staining the roots with trypan blue [14].

The data obtained from the pot experiment was subjected to analysis of variance by randomized complete block design and treatment means were separated by Duncan's multiple range DMR test [18].

RESULTS

Alginate entrapped AM mass inoculum

The pH of the different carrier materials varied from an acidic to alkaline range (pH 6.5 to 8.2). The moisture content of wet beads was 78.05- 84 per cent and the moisture content of dry alginate was between 20.2 and 23.5 per cent (Table 1). Perlite based wet AM alginate beads had highest number of propagules of AM (3.8/g) inoculum followed by soilrite based wet alginate entrapped AM inoculum (2.9/g). Among the dry AM alginate beads, the beads with perlite as carrier ranked first with 22.2 propagules of AM per g of the inoculum, while vermiculate based alginate entrapped AM beads had only 7.6 propagules of AM per g of beads (Table 1).

Table 1. pH of the different carrier materials and moisture content of the wet and dry AM alginate beads.

Carrier material	pH	Moisture content of wet AM alginate beads (%)	Moisture content of dry AM alginate beads (%)	*IPg ⁻¹	
				Wet beads	Dry beads
Perlite	7.4	82.20	23.5	3.8	22.2
Soilrite	7.2	84.00	20.4	2.9	16.3
Vermiculate	8.2	78.05	20.2	1.3	7.6
Talc	7.9	82.05	22.7	2.2	15.1
Sand and Soil (Control)	6.5	--	--	52.8	

Effect of sodium alginate entrapped native AMF inoculum on root colonization and spore number in garlic varieties

Inoculation with the AM fungus, *G. aggregatum* as alginate entrapped inoculum produced plants with greater height, number of leaves, plant biomass and sizes of bulb compared to control in which plants grown in sand and soils without alginate entrapment having only indigenous AM fungi. Maximum root colonization and more number of spores were encountered in the root zone soils of the plants inoculated with sodium alginate based dry inoculum compared to control inoculated with native AMF (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculum (*Glomus aggregatum*) on growth parameters of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates).

Garlic variety	Root length(cm)					Shoot length(cm)					Number of leaves				
	Carrier material wet					Carrier material wet					Carrier material wet				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Wet inoculum															
Benthatty local	9.14 ^a	9.06 ^{ab}	8.75 ^b	7.64 ^c	7.12 ^c	44.04 ^a	43.48 ^b	44.17 ^a	43.27 ^b	38.45 ^c	7.94 ^a	7.64 ^a	8.52 ^b	7.14 ^a	7.15 ^a
Sholur local	8.24 ^{ab}	8.74 ^a	8.84 ^a	8.15 ^{ab}	7.91 ^b	42.05 ^{ab}	43.15 ^{ab}	44.26 ^a	41.87 ^b	38.95 ^c	6.54 ^c	7.43 ^b	8.58 ^a	7.21 ^b	6.52 ^c
Thummanatty local	9.61 ^a	9.16 ^{ab}	9.48 ^{ab}	9.38 ^{ab}	8.91 ^b	38.09 ^c	40.91 ^b	41.44 ^{ab}	42.63 ^a	36.58 ^d	7.56 ^b	8.19 ^a	8.18 ^a	7.14 ^a	7.11 ^b
Nanjanadu local	6.88 ^b	7.67 ^{ab}	8.47 ^a	6.83 ^{bc}	6.11 ^c	41.53 ^b	42.59 ^{ab}	44.38 ^a	44.58 ^a	37.78 ^c	7.13 ^a	7.25 ^a	7.41 ^a	7.21 ^a	6.97 ^b
Kollimalai local	9.78 ^{ab}	9.92 ^a	9.53 ^b	9.47 ^{abc}	8.96 ^c	42.27 ^c	46.14 ^b	47.16 ^a	45.87 ^{bc}	40.12 ^d	8.62 ^a	8.56 ^a	8.14 ^a	7.96 ^{ab}	7.17 ^b
Kilkundah local	8.47 ^b	8.92 ^{ab}	9.28 ^a	8.17 ^{bc}	7.92 ^c	54.24 ^b	55.27 ^a	54.37 ^b	52.86 ^c	52.36 ^c	6.25 ^b	7.56 ^a	7.23 ^a	6.89 ^{ab}	6.13 ^c
Nedugula local	7.26 ^{ab}	7.67 ^{ab}	7.84 ^a	7.01 ^b	6.89 ^c	62.16 ^a	48.26 ^b	44.34 ^c	44.84 ^c	42.26 ^d	7.24 ^{ab}	7.64 ^{ab}	8.51 ^a	7.23 ^{ab}	7.11 ^b
Dry inoculum															
Benthatty local	8.91 ^b	9.21 ^a	9.17 ^a	7.83 ^c	7.12 ^c	43.1 ^a	40.1 ^d	42.27 ^b	41.57 ^c	38.45 ^a	7.31 ^{bc}	7.25 ^c	7.86 ^a	7.42 ^b	7.15 ^d
Sholur local	9.22 ^a	8.66 ^b	8.53 ^b	8.47 ^b	7.91 ^c	42.5 ^b	41.2 ^c	44.46 ^a	40.66 ^d	38.95 ^c	7.54 ^a	7.25 ^b	7.25 ^b	6.76 ^c	6.52 ^c
Thummanatty local	9.96 ^a	9.25 ^{ab}	9.64 ^a	9.09 ^b	8.91 ^b	37.5 ^c	40.1 ^b	40.24 ^b	41.35 ^a	36.58 ^d	8.14 ^a	7.24 ^b	8.56 ^a	7.45 ^b	7.11 ^b
Nanjanadu local	7.53 ^b	7.33 ^b	8.19 ^a	6.94 ^{bc}	6.11 ^c	41.4 ^b	41.3 ^b	40.68 ^c	45.17 ^a	37.78 ^d	7.12 ^b	8.12 ^a	8.10 ^a	7.25 ^b	6.97 ^b
Kollimalai local	9.87 ^a	9.27 ^b	9.68 ^{ab}	9.83 ^a	8.96 ^c	42.0 ^c	45.2 ^b	47.45 ^a	47.55 ^a	40.12 ^d	8.13 ^a	8.13 ^a	8.33 ^a	8.45 ^a	7.96 ^b
Kilkundah local	8.64 ^{ab}	8.69 ^{ab}	9.43 ^a	8.57 ^b	7.92 ^c	59.3 ^a	54.5 ^b	55.45 ^{ab}	54.67 ^b	52.36 ^c	7.65 ^a	7.35 ^a	7.45 ^a	6.54 ^b	6.13 ^b
Nedugula local	8.26 ^a	7.92 ^{ab}	7.57 ^b	6.81 ^c	6.89 ^c	44.2 ^c	49.3 ^a	46.38 ^b	46.17 ^b	42.26 ^d	7.65 ^a	7.45 ^a	7.37 ^a	7.56 ^a	7.11 ^a

Means of each row followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P<0.05) from each other according to DMR test. P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

Per cent mycorrhizal root colonization (79.26%) was maximum in Kollimalai local variety inoculated with perlite based dry inoculum followed by Thummanatty local variety with similar inoculation (66.11%). Root colonization was observed minimum in the control plants but it was statistically insignificant in many test plants. The Kollimalai local variety treated with perlite based inoculum showed maximum number of 560 spores and the lowest number of spores (114) was noticed in the root zone of control plants of Benthatty local variety (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of inoculation with different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculums (*Glomus aggregatum*) on growth parameters of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates).

Garlic variety	Fresh weight shoot(g)					Dry weight shoot(g)				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Wet inoculum										
Benthatty local	36.12 ^a	32.56 ^c	34.35 ^b	32.54 ^c	28.65 ^d	17.32 ^a	15.32 ^{ab}	15.67 ^{ab}	16.49 ^b	13.81 ^c
Sholur local	34.24 ^a	31.68 ^b	32.69 ^{ab}	29.92 ^c	29.84 ^c	16.58 ^a	14.25 ^{ab}	13.56 ^b	14.35 ^{ab}	12.54 ^b
Thummanatty local	38.39 ^b	39.36 ^{ab}	41.84 ^a	37.67 ^c	29.73 ^d	17.35 ^b	21.34 ^a	21.61 ^a	17.19 ^b	13.16 ^c
Nanjanadu local	32.21 ^c	33.68 ^c	36.87 ^a	34.31 ^b	28.74 ^d	18.25 ^a	16.94 ^{ab}	18.31 ^a	15.28 ^b	13.61 ^c
Kollimalai local	42.36 ^a	39.58 ^{ab}	36.69 ^b	39.33 ^{ab}	36.14 ^b	20.33 ^b	24.13 ^a	17.62 ^c	20.34 ^b	15.27 ^d
Kilkundah local	32.15 ^b	30.94 ^{bc}	28.91 ^c	37.61 ^a	25.26 ^d	15.89 ^c	14.65 ^b	17.41 ^a	14.61 ^b	11.34 ^d
Nedugula local	29.24 ^{bc}	27.89 ^c	32.68 ^b	34.63 ^a	26.49 ^d	16.54 ^c	17.35 ^b	16.82 ^c	18.60 ^a	14.82 ^d
Dry inoculum										
Benthatty local	34.73 ^a	33.54 ^{ab}	31.52 ^b	33.18 ^{ab}	28.65 ^c	17.21 ^a	16.31 ^b	14.25 ^d	15.52 ^c	13.81 ^c
Sholur local	38.76 ^a	37.65 ^{ab}	31.64 ^c	36.52 ^b	29.92 ^c	20.27 ^a	19.52 ^a	16.38 ^b	18.62 ^{ab}	12.54 ^c
Thummanatty local	41.52 ^a	42.51 ^a	36.41 ^b	37.19 ^b	29.73 ^c	22.63 ^a	16.32 ^b	14.69 ^c	14.35 ^c	13.16 ^d
Nanjanadu local	36.64 ^a	32.54 ^b	32.61 ^b	30.45 ^c	28.74 ^d	18.65 ^a	16.57 ^b	16.28 ^b	14.68 ^c	13.61 ^d
Kollimalai local	42.62 ^a	39.12 ^{ab}	40.11 ^{ab}	38.71 ^b	36.14 ^c	21.41 ^a	20.91 ^b	17.53 ^c	20.67 ^b	15.27 ^d
Kilkundah local	35.43 ^b	36.17 ^a	36.42 ^a	27.85 ^c	22.26 ^d	18.62 ^{ab}	16.37 ^b	13.51 ^c	19.63 ^a	11.34 ^d
Nedugula local	38.41 ^a	35.63 ^b	35.94 ^b	35.69 ^b	26.49 ^c	20.58 ^a	18.43 ^{ab}	16.25 ^c	17.51 ^b	14.82 ^d

Means of each row followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from each other according to DMR test.

P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

Effect of sodium alginate entrapped inoculum on plant growth of Garlic varieties

In general inoculation of soil with perlite based dry and wet beads resulted in plants with maximum height (root length and shoot length) and number of leaves. Inoculation of soil with perlite based dry beads resulted in plants with maximum height and plant biomass. The length of the shoot was varied from 36.58 cm/plant to 62.16 cm/plant and the length of the root was also varied from 6.11cm/plant to 9.96 cm/plant (Table. 4). The Nedugula local variety exhibits the maximum shoot length and the minimum shoot length was observed in the control plant of Thummanatty local.

Table 4. Effect of inoculation with different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculums (*Glomus aggregatum*) on growth parameters of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates).

Garlic variety	Fresh weight bulb with root(g)					Dry weight bulb with root(g)				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Wet inoculum										
Benthatty local	50.54 ^a	49.21 ^b	49.19 ^b	47.24 ^c	42.25 ^d	26.35 ^a	24.36 ^b	24.36 ^b	23.58 ^c	20.65 ^d
Sholur local	44.61 ^b	46.41 ^{ab}	47.25 ^a	46.97 ^{ab}	40.36 ^c	21.52 ^c	23.52 ^{ab}	24.52 ^a	22.65 ^b	19.79 ^c
Thummanatty local	52.32 ^c	56.18 ^a	54.36 ^b	53.84 ^{bc}	49.54 ^d	26.35 ^b	29.64 ^a	27.65 ^{ab}	27.86 ^{ab}	25.60 ^c
Nanjanadu local	50.21 ^b	52.26 ^a	50.48 ^b	51.72 ^{ab}	49.25 ^b	27.58 ^a	26.33 ^a	25.68 ^b	25.37 ^b	25.39 ^b
Kollimalai local	60.81 ^{ab}	61.45 ^a	59.72 ^b	60.54 ^{ab}	54.58 ^c	30.19 ^b	31.56 ^a	31.56 ^a	31.52 ^a	26.51 ^c
Kilkundah local	24.84 ^c	35.39 ^a	31.31 ^{ab}	29.31 ^b	22.64 ^d	13.61 ^c	18.65 ^a	16.93 ^b	16.52 ^b	11.93 ^d
Nedugula local	26.51 ^a	24.43 ^b	22.63 ^c	25.29 ^{ab}	21.27 ^c	12.97 ^b	13.74 ^a	12.68 ^b	13.94 ^a	10.19 ^c
Dry inoculum										
Benthatty local	52.36 ^a	46.52 ^c	50.12 ^b	44.21 ^d	42.25 ^e	26.18 ^a	24.81 ^b	26.35 ^a	23.42 ^c	20.65 ^d
Sholur local	43.56 ^a	42.31 ^{ab}	40.18 ^b	40.14 ^b	40.36 ^b	21.68 ^b	22.65 ^a	21.81 ^b	20.61 ^{bc}	19.79 ^c
Thummanatty local	52.41 ^b	50.21 ^{bc}	53.36 ^a	49.76 ^c	49.54 ^c	26.34 ^b	26.41 ^b	27.12 ^a	25.63 ^c	25.60 ^c
Nanjanadu local	49.43 ^b	49.34 ^b	52.81 ^a	49.61 ^b	49.25 ^b	26.65 ^b	26.42 ^b	27.14 ^a	25.78 ^c	25.39 ^c
Kollimalai local	62.24 ^a	59.18 ^b	60.53 ^{ab}	58.46 ^b	54.58 ^c	31.52 ^a	30.14 ^b	30.41 ^b	30.67 ^b	26.51 ^c
Kilkundah local	36.27 ^a	30.21 ^c	29.31 ^c	32.21 ^b	22.64 ^d	16.25 ^b	16.54 ^b	16.51 ^b	18.15 ^a	11.93 ^c
Nedugula local	36.33 ^a	33.54 ^c	35.14 ^b	32.54 ^c	21.27 ^d	19.61 ^a	17.82 ^b	19.30 ^a	16.21 ^c	10.19 ^d

Means of each row followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from each other according to DMR test. P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

There was no significant difference in the number of leaves of alginate entrapped inoculated plants and control plants. The maximum number of 8.62 leaves per plant was observed in Kollimalai local plant treated with perlite based dry inoculum and the minimum number of 6.13 leaves per plant was observed in the control plant of the Kilkundah local variety (Table 4). The plant fresh weight (shoot and bulb with root) was maximum in plant inoculated with perlite based dry inoculum and the minimum was observed in the control. The maximum shoot fresh weight of 42.62 g/plant was observed in the Kollimalai local variety treated with perlite based dry inoculum while the minimum shoot fresh weight of 22.26g/plant was observed in the control plant of Kilkundah local variety (Table 5). Dry biomass of plants inoculated with either dry alginate entrapped inoculum or wet alginate entrapped inoculum were statistically insignificant in many results. The shoot dry weight observed maximum in the Thummanatty local (22.63 g/plant) while the minimum noticed in the control plant of Kilkundah local (11.34g/plant) variety (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of inoculation with different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculums (*Glomus aggregatum*) on bulb size of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates).

Garlic variety	Bulb equatorial diameter(cm)					Bulb polar diameter(cm)					Neck thickness(cm)				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Wet inoculum															
Benthatty local	4.25	4.32	4.58	4.81	3.94	3.54	3.58	3.41	3.67	2.87	3.41	3.47	3.58	3.45	3.11
Sholur local	4.11	4.85	3.96	4.12	3.75	3.05	3.67	2.84	3.98	2.64	3.56	3.15	3.65	3.56	3.16
Thummanatty local	4.61	4.52	4.21	3.84	3.67	3.52	3.48	3.51	2.91	2.56	3.54	3.65	3.84	3.47	3.16
Nanjanadu local	4.14	3.98	4.20	3.84	3.52	3.14	2.96	3.85	2.89	2.51	3.10	3.17	3.54	3.52	3.22
Kollimalai local	5.11	5.13	5.16	4.85	4.12	4.90	4.54	4.51	3.82	3.62	3.15	3.12	3.65	3.45	3.14
Kilkundah local	4.12	4.11	3.87	3.76	3.59	3.12	3.26	2.86	2.64	2.51	3.14	3.14	3.54	3.54	3.10
Nedugula local	3.12	3.24	3.10	2.96	2.84	2.61	2.11	2.16	2.13	2.10	2.45	2.34	2.45	2.65	2.13
Dry inoculum															
Benthatty local	4.21	3.92	4.51	3.84	3.94	3.94	3.11	3.42	2.81	2.87	3.42	3.12	3.45	3.57	3.11
Sholur local	4.52	4.47	3.91	3.96	3.75	3.44	3.36	2.87	2.87	2.64	3.41	3.56	3.46	3.65	3.16
Thummanatty local	4.21	4.32	4.11	3.84	3.67	3.87	3.92	3.54	2.96	2.56	3.56	3.23	3.54	3.85	3.16
Nanjanadu local	3.95	4.19	3.85	4.65	3.52	2.97	3.86	2.74	3.91	2.51	3.91	3.65	3.52	3.54	3.22
Kollimalai local	5.42	4.91	4.86	5.13	4.12	4.92	3.94	3.57	4.83	3.62	3.95	3.75	3.56	3.58	3.14
Kilkundah local	4.54	3.91	4.11	3.96	3.59	3.45	2.96	3.13	3.06	2.51	3.16	3.65	3.44	3.78	3.10
Nedugula local	3.52	3.41	3.59	2.91	2.84	2.42	2.362.	2.45	2.19	2.10	2.35	2.14	2.41	2.13	2.13

P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

The fresh weight of garlic bulb with root was varied in the different varieties. The maximum fresh weight of bulb with root 62.24 g/plant was observed in the Kollimalai local treated with perlite based dry inoculum and the minimum of 21.27 g/plant was noticed in Nedugula local variety (Table 6). The dry weight of bulb with root also varied in the different varieties treated with different carrier based inoculum. Maximum dry weight of bulb observed in Kollimalai local (31.52g/plant) and the minimum was noticed in the control plant of Nedugula local (10.19 g/plant) (Table 6).

Table 6. Effect of inoculation with different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculums (*Glomus aggregatum*) on NPK content of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates).

Garlic variety	N content(%)					P content(%)					K content(%)				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Wet inoculum															
Benthatty local	1.45	1.34	1.52	1.44	1.25	0.198	0.196	0.189	0.192	0.183	0.756	0.784	0.754	0.766	0.741
Sholur local	1.54	1.56	1.53	1.45	1.24	0.178	0.156	0.167	0.169	0.146	0.742	0.751	0.756	0.745	0.723
Thummanatty local	1.87	1.75	1.86	1.79	1.68	0.196	0.194	0.192	0.190	0.186	0.772	0.777	0.776	0.791	0.769
Nanjanadu local	1.56	1.65	1.42	1.41	1.13	0.184	0.174	0.183	0.170	0.165	0.745	0.756	0.744	0.756	0.733
Kollimalai local	1.86	1.86	1.88	1.98	1.26	0.268	0.238	0.265	0.236	0.224	0.842	0.854	0.861	0.848	0.836
Kilkundah local	1.65	1.42	1.54	1.36	1.12	0.201	0.192	0.186	0.184	0.180	0.764	0.776	0.768	0.774	0.756
Nedugula local	1.45	1.23	1.33	1.42	1.02	0.196	0.178	0.186	0.184	0.172	0.785	0.796	0.766	0.759	0.750
Dry inoculum															
Benthatty local	1.43	1.41	1.46	1.48	1.25	0.201	0.192	0.194	0.198	0.183	0.758	0.774	0.765	0.758	0.741
Sholur local	1.52	1.36	1.42	1.33	1.24	0.176	0.154	0.165	0.154	0.146	0.732	0.730	0.756	0.739	0.723
Thummanatty local	1.79	1.86	1.84	1.74	1.68	0.199	0.197	0.191	0.191	0.186	0.775	0.781	0.786	0.779	0.769
Nanjanadu local	1.32	1.26	1.56	1.47	1.13	0.210	0.186	0.193	0.185	0.165	0.749	0.755	0.765	0.754	0.733
Kollimalai local	2.05	1.89	1.98	1.94	1.26	0.297	0.264	0.274	0.236	0.224	0.869	0.854	0.866	0.845	0.836
Kilkundah local	1.43	1.47	1.46	1.39	1.12	0.198	0.194	0.189	0.192	0.180	0.785	0.764	0.779	0.781	0.756
Nedugula local	1.29	1.36	1.52	1.43	1.02	0.192	0.191	0.184	0.184	0.172	0.764	0.784	0.772	0.761	0.750

P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

The size of the garlic bulb is also differing from variety to variety. The equatorial and polar diameters of the bulbs were measured. The equatorial diameter noticed high (5.42cm/bulb) in Kollimalai local variety treated with perlite based dry inoculum and the minimum(2.84cm/bulb) was observed in the control of Nedugula local variety(Table 7). Similarly the highest(4.92cm/bulb) polar diameter noticed in Kollimalai local treated with perlite based dry inoculum and the lowest(2.10cm/bulb) was observed in the control plant of Nedugula local (Table 7). Neck thickness also showed the similar results that the Kollimalai local showed the maximum of 3.95 cm/plant and the minimum of 2.13cm/plant was observed in the control of Nedugula local(Table 7).

Table 7. Effect of inoculation with different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculums (*Glomus aggregatum*) on % root colonization of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates)

Garlic variety	% root colonization									
	Carrier material wet					Carrier material dry				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Benthatty local	42.56 ^a	33.54 ^b	38.64 ^{ab}	41.29 ^a	32.15 ^b	40.21 ^a	36.52 ^b	39.24 ^{ab}	35.26 ^{bc}	32.15 ^c
Sholur local	45.65 ^a	44.21 ^a	40.32 ^{ab}	31.54 ^b	33.68 ^c	45.32 ^a	43.56 ^{ab}	40.21 ^b	36.61 ^{bc}	33.68 ^c
Thummanatty local	64.21 ^a	56.84 ^{ab}	53.46 ^b	49.94 ^c	41.23 ^d	66.11 ^a	63.54 ^{ab}	57.23 ^b	49.91 ^c	41.23 ^d
Nanjanadu local	39.86 ^b	32.87 ^c	39.12 ^b	42.31 ^a	31.42 ^c	48.32 ^a	39.54 ^c	42.58 ^b	43.68 ^b	31.42 ^d
Kollimalai local	70.51 ^a	65.71 ^b	59.36 ^c	63.54 ^{ab}	51.42 ^d	79.26 ^a	63.52 ^{ab}	60.54 ^b	54.47 ^{bc}	51.42 ^c
Kilkundah local	49.63 ^a	49.26 ^a	41.35 ^b	42.51 ^b	39.52 ^c	46.31 ^a	43.65 ^{ab}	39.57 ^c	42.96 ^b	39.52 ^c
Nedugula local	54.22 ^a	51.32 ^{ab}	49.63 ^b	48.24 ^{bc}	45.64 ^c	54.11 ^a	52.23 ^{ab}	50.41 ^{ab}	45.86 ^b	45.64 ^b

Means of each row followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from each other according to DMR test.

P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

Effect of sodium alginate entrapped native AMF inoculum with different carrier materials on nutritional status of garlic varieties

Sodium alginate entrapped native AMF inoculum resulted in increased plant N, P and K content of garlic varieties (Table 8). It is well known that enhanced nutritional status of a plant is manifested in its improved growth. The nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content was high (2.05 %, 0.297 % and 0.869 % respectively per plant) in plants inoculated with perlite based dry inoculum (Table 8). The low level of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (1.02%, 0.146% and 0.723% per plant respectively) was observed in control plants (Table 8). There was a significant increase in plant P content because of inoculation with alginate entrapped AM inoculum of *G. aggregatum* compared to the control (Table 8). The maximum (0.297%) amount of phosphorus was noticed in the perlite based dry inoculum in Kollimalai local treated plants.

Table 8. Effect of inoculation with different carrier based alginate entrapped AM fungal inoculums (*Glomus aggregatum*) on spore number of garlic varieties (Mean of five replicates)

Garlic variety	Spore number/100 g of soil									
	Carrier material wet					Carrier material dry				
	P	S	V	T	C	P	S	V	T	C
Benthatty local	213 ^c	250 ^b	271 ^a	174 ^d	114 ^e	274 ^b	254 ^c	301 ^a	294 ^{ab}	114 ^d
Sholur local	294 ^a	210 ^{bc}	251 ^b	211 ^{bc}	186 ^c	306 ^a	304 ^a	265 ^b	254 ^c	186 ^d
Thummanatty local	451 ^{ab}	501 ^a	521 ^a	467 ^{ab}	298 ^b	524 ^a	512 ^{ab}	469 ^b	473 ^b	298 ^c
Nanjanadu local	280 ^{ab}	241 ^b	214 ^{bc}	296 ^a	181 ^c	315 ^a	321 ^a	245 ^b	215 ^c	181 ^d
Kollimalai local	512 ^{ab}	542 ^a	520 ^{ab}	493 ^b	412 ^c	560 ^a	496 ^b	497 ^b	521 ^{ab}	412 ^c
Kilkundah local	305 ^c	365 ^b	374 ^{ab}	395 ^a	212 ^d	295 ^a	254 ^b	213 ^c	248 ^b	212 ^d
Nedugula local	432 ^b	451 ^a	423 ^{abc}	398 ^c	330 ^d	406 ^a	389 ^{ab}	365 ^b	411 ^a	330 ^c

Means of each row followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from each other according to DMR test.

P – Perlite based AMF inoculum; S – Soilrite based AMF inoculum; V – Vermiculite based AMF inoculum; T – Talc based AMF inoculum; C – Control

DISCUSSION

Sodium alginate entrapped native AMF inoculum production

Perlite, Kaolinite, Soilrite, vermiculite and bentonite have been tried earlier as carrier materials for immobilization. Among the carrier based wet alginate beads, perlite-alginate beads had the highest propagules of AM fungi followed by soilrite based alginate entrapped AM inoculum. Perlite is a relatively inert material, light in weight with a neutral pH and it has been used earlier as a carrier material in alginate beads for Rhizobium^[19] Alginate is also an inert material and offers a mild condition for entrapment^[20]. The favourable pH required for the spore germination and effective association of *Glomus aggregatum* is around seven^[21] which is the pH of perlite too (Table 1). This could be the reason for the survival of highest number of AM propagules in the perlite based AM alginate beads.

Effect of sodium alginate entrapped native AMF in root colonization and spore number

The present study clearly indicates that alginate entrapped mycorrhizal inoculation of different garlic varieties is beneficial. It is noteworthy that the AM fungal species screened was native endophytes which would have well adapted to local conditions. Alginate entrapped AM inoculum showed high root colonization and spore numbers (Table 2 and 3). Similar observations were also recorded by various authors^[22,23,24].

Effect of sodium alginate entrapped native AMF on growth of garlic varieties

The root inoculum of the AM fungus, *Glomus aggregatum* immobilized in alginate beads^[25]. They reported that inoculation of leek plantlets with AM fungal entrapped alginate beads stored at 4°C for a period of one month induced colonization of roots by fungus. The present study gives further information on the number of AM propagules in the alginate entrapped inoculum and its influence on the growth and nutrition of garlic varieties used as a host.

The plant height, number of leaves, plant biomass and bulb size was higher in garlic varieties inoculated with perlite based alginate entrapped *Glomus aggregatum*. These parameters were least in control plants (Table- 4-7). This may be due to the garlic varietal differences^[22].

Effect of sodium alginate entrapped native AMF inoculum on nutrition status of garlic varieties

As a result of symbiotic association between AMF and host plant, phosphorus content also has an effect on growth parameters in plants ^[26,27]. Phosphorus plays an important role as an energy carrier during photosynthesis ^[28]. Many workers have reported greater uptake of P, Zn, Cu, Mn and Fe due to AMF inoculation in medicinal plants ^[29,30].

In the present study, higher levels of nutrients in perlite based alginate beads inoculated plants might have resulted in improved plant growth and bulb yield (Table 4-7). Such a variation in the plant nutrient status in relation to the fungal species for other medicinal plants is well documented. However, the results of the present investigation clearly indicated the superior efficiency of alginate entrapped *Glomus aggregatum* inoculum increasing not only P status of plants but also Nitrogen and potassium contents (Table 8) which, in turn, improves plant growth and biomass yield of garlic varieties. The increase in growth and nutritional status is also related to the per cent root colonization apart from several soils and environmental factors ^[31].

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study clearly indicates that the perlite based dry alginate entrapped *G. aggregatum* inoculum performed better in improving growth and nutrition of garlic varieties. It was noticed that the plant growth, total biomass, mycorrhizal root colonization, spore number and NPK contents were maximum in the alginate entrapped inoculum treated plants compare to the control. Hence the present investigation recommends that the native strain of *G. aggregatum* along with the sodium alginate entrapped inoculum is suitable for the cultivation of native garlic varieties in Nilgiris District.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge to the University Grants Commission (Project Ref. No. MRP-3447/10 (MRP/UGC- SERO), for financial support and also to the farmers of Nilgiris who helped us to collect the samples.

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